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Influence of Parenting Styles on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of parenting styles on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria, using a descriptive survey design. A sample of 400 students was selected, and data were collected with the Parenting Styles and Academic Adjustment Questionnaire (PSAAQ), which showed a reliability coefficient of 0.77. Data were analysed using mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square tests at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful parenting styles each significantly influence students' academic adjustment. It was recommended that parents adopt the authoritative style, as it provides a balance of discipline and support that enhances students' confidence, motivation, and adjustment to academic demands.

Keywords: Parenting Styles, Authoritative Parenting Style, Authoritarian Parenting Style, Permissive Parenting Style, Neglectful Parenting Style, Academic Adjustment.

INTRODUCTION

Adjusting to the demands of school life has always been one of the most pressing challenges for students, particularly at the senior secondary school level where academic expectations increase significantly. At this stage, students are confronted with heavy subject loads, preparation for external examinations, and the pressure to meet parental and societal expectations. Many of them also struggle with balancing school work with personal interests, peer influence, and the rapid emotional and social changes that come with adolescence. It is within this mix of challenges that academic adjustment becomes critical, as the way students adapt often determines whether they thrive or falter in their educational journey.

Academic adjustment is the process by which students become accustomed to academic demands in school. It is the ongoing interaction between students and all academic aspects of the school environment, including instruction, studying, assessment, and the norms that support learning. The timeframe and ease of this process differ across individuals and involve both mental and behavioural adaptation (George, 2020). Students who are well adjusted academically feel a sense of belonging in school, experience comfort and security, show minimal anxiety, obey rules that enable learning, listen to instructions, relate well with others, and regulate emotions in ways that support study. Such students sustain interest in learning and are motivated to participate in classroom and co-curricular activities that reinforce academic growth (Margetts, 2015). In this sense, academic adjustment captures students' interest in schoolwork, their engagement with learning, and their achievement outcomes, all of which are shaped by personal abilities, skills, and the interpersonal environment that surrounds them (Ladd, 1996).

For many students, adjustment is not a smooth process. Some cope well by managing their study schedules, seeking help when needed, and developing resilience against failure, while others become overwhelmed by stress, disengaged from learning, or inconsistent in their academic habits. Studies have shown that students who experience persistent difficulties in adapting to academic demands are more likely to record low achievement, irregular attendance, and in severe cases, withdrawal from school (Credé & Niehorster, 2012; Olowodunoye & Titus, 2016). Notably, adjustment has been observed to be shaped by factors outside the classroom. The school environment provides only part of the picture; the home and family remain central to how students respond to academic pressures. Adolescents often carry into the classroom the emotional and psychological effects of their family experiences (Dwairy, 2010). One of the factors arising from the family that influences academic adjustment is parenting styles (Dwairy, 2004; Okeke, 2015; Pinguart & Kauser, 2018).

Tam, Chong, Kadirvelu & Khoo (2012) asserted that parenting style is a pattern of attitudes and behaviours that parents exhibit in raising their children. Gawas (2021) describes parenting style as the methods parents consider when developing children's social behaviours, while Naima (2012) frames it as parents' behaviour toward their children and their awareness of the parent-child relationship. According to Shahlal, Isa and Kecek (2021), Baumrind (1967) introduced three parenting styles, namely authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive. Maccoby and Martin (1983) extended this framework by adding neglectful or uninvolved parenting (Shahlal, Isa & Kecek, 2021).

Authoritative parenting style reflects a balanced combination of demandingness and responsiveness, and it guides children in a goal oriented and disciplined way by explaining the reasons behind rules (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). Authoritative parents maintain high expectations for achievement and maturity, yet remain warm and responsive. They set rules and boundaries through open discussion, provide guidance, and use reasoning. By offering explanations, they cultivate children's awareness of values, morals, and goals. The authoritative parent seeks to direct the child's activities in a rational, issue-oriented manner, encourages two-way communication, shares the reasoning behind policies, and listens to objections when the child resists. Both autonomous self-will and disciplined conformity are valued (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). Studies affirm that adolescents raised in authoritative homes often exhibit better study habits, stronger motivation, and greater adaptability to the pressures of schoolwork compared to peers from other parenting backgrounds (Sahithya et al., 2019; Pinguart & Gerke, 2019). In situations where students face heavy academic workloads and examination pressure, authoritative parenting creates a balance between discipline and emotional support, helping students to manage stress, persist in challenging tasks, and maintain a positive orientation toward learning. This balance appears particularly important as students who experience authoritative parenting are more likely to stay consistent in attendance, concentrate better during lessons, and perform well in assessments, indicating that this style of parenting fosters the personal and social resources needed for healthy academic adjustment (Abuhammad, 2020; Baumrind, 2016; Ayonrinde, 2021).

Authoritarian parenting style is marked by highly restrictive and demanding practices. Authoritarian parents shape, control, and evaluate the child's behaviour and attitudes according to absolute standards, often theologically motivated or derived from higher authority (Darko & Gyasi, 2019). It combines high levels of parental control with low responsiveness. Although it shares high demands with the authoritative style, authoritarian parenting requires blind obedience. Communication is one way through rules and orders, and attempts at reasoning are treated as backtalk. Discipline is stern, often involving harsh punishment, including corporal punishment, to control behaviour. Methods are coercive, that is, arbitrary, preemptory, domineering, and focused on status distinctions. Such parents are unresponsive to needs and are generally not nurturing, frequently justifying harshness as tough love (Shahlal, Isa & Kecek, 2021). Recent research indicates that authoritarian parenting tends to increase academic stress, reduce intrinsic motivation, and foster negative attitudes toward learning, which ultimately undermine students' capacity to cope with academic challenges (Pinguart & Gerke, 2019; Ayonrinde, 2021). For adolescents in secondary schools, where adjustment requires not only following school rules but also developing self-

regulation and problem-solving skills, the rigid control of authoritarian parents can limit creativity and lead to anxiety in academic tasks (Abuhammad, 2020).

Parents that adopt the permissive parenting style are relatively non-controlling, make few demands, and allow children to make their own decisions and regulate their own behaviour. They refuse to impose rules and standards, encouraging self-regulation, and they respond to impulses and desires in an acceptant and affirmative manner without punitive action (Uji, Sakamoto, Adachi & Kitamura, 2014). Children raised this way enjoy high freedom with few restrictions when no physical harm is apparent. Expectations are low, the relationship resembles friendship, and only minimal limits are imposed (Berg, 2011). Recent studies have shown that permissive parenting is frequently associated with lower academic achievement and weaker adjustment to school demands, as students may struggle with time management, responsibility, and resilience in the face of academic challenges (Mulia et al., 2019; Muriithi & Mweru, 2020). Adolescents in permissive households often experience a sense of comfort at home but may lack the self-regulation required to cope with the structured and demanding nature of secondary school environments (Pinquart, 2017).

Neglectful or uninvolved parenting style is both undemanding and unresponsive. It is identified by few parental demands, little communication, and low responsiveness. Parents often disengage from their children's lives beyond provision of basic needs. Williams and Sánchez (2012) note that uninvolved parents are self-involved or overly busy, which limits their ability to provide basic care consistently. They expect children to take charge of their own destinies. Such parents show very little love, attention, mental and moral support, protection, or supervision. Limited time with the child reduces mutual understanding and weakens the parent-child relationship. Some neglect occurs unintentionally due to work pressures. Children raised in neglectful households often face difficulties with self-regulation, motivation, and persistence, which are essential for coping with the pressures of academic life. Studies have shown that neglectful parenting is strongly associated with lower academic performance, poor study habits, and increased risk of disengagement from school activities (Valente et al., 2016; Pinquart, 2017). Without parental involvement, students may lack encouragement to set goals, develop effective study routines, or seek help when faced with challenges, leading to weak adaptation to school expectations. Moreover, neglectful parenting has been linked to emotional insecurity and lower self-esteem, factors that further hinder students' ability to concentrate and thrive in demanding academic environments (Akhter et al., 2018).

While academic success is closely tied to students' adjustment to academics, the home remains the first context where the foundations of adjustment are laid. Parenting style is particularly influential because it shapes habits, attitudes, and expectations that students carry into the academic setting. Given these dynamics, the present study investigates how authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful parenting styles influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Many students in secondary schools today struggle with adjusting to the academic demands placed on them. Cases of declining study habits, inability to concentrate during lessons, poor time management, and lack of motivation to engage with schoolwork are increasingly reported among adolescents. Teachers often lament that even intelligent students fail to reach their potential because they lack the right balance of discipline, guidance, and emotional support from home. Peer influence, examination anxiety, and the pressure to perform are further compounded by the absence of strong parental involvement, leaving many students overwhelmed. The result is seen in poor grades, rising cases of absenteeism, and in some situations, outright school dropout. These issues are not just academic challenges but have long-term implications for students' career opportunities and life trajectories. One key factor that has been consistently identified as shaping how well students adjust to school is parenting style. Parents differ greatly in the ways they set rules, provide guidance, and offer emotional support to their children, and these differences are reflected in students' ability to cope with academic stress. In Nigerian, where education is highly valued as a pathway to social mobility, poor adjustment among students remains a

worrisome concern. It is against this backdrop that the current study aims to investigate the influence of parenting styles on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered to guide the study:

1. How does authoritative parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria?
2. How does authoritarian parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria?
3. How does permissive parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria?
4. How does neglectful parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and shall be tested at 0.5 level of significance:

1. Authoritative parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.
2. Authoritarian parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.
3. Permissive parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.
4. Neglectful parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population comprised public secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. A sample of 400 students was selected using the Taro Yamane formula for determining appropriate sample size from a known population. The Parenting Styles and Academic Adjustment Questionnaire (PSAAQ) was developed and administered to collect data about students' school adjustment. The questionnaire was made up of 20 items and followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement or disagreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted, and the reliability coefficient was calculated using Cronbach's Alpha. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.77, indicating a satisfactory level of reliability for the study. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to address the research questions. Hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness-of-fit test at the 0.05 level of significance. A criterion mean of 2.50 was used for decision-making; scores below 2.50 were interpreted as negative responses or disagreement.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *How does authoritative parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Analysis of Influence of Authoritative Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	My parents encourage me to express my opinions about schoolwork.	100	180	64	56	2.81	.968	Accepted
2	My parents support me with both discipline and guidance in my academics.	200	144	24	32	3.28	.896	Accepted
3	I feel confident to discuss my academic challenges with my parents.	156	180	44	20	3.18	.818	Accepted
4	My parents set clear academic expectations while also considering my feelings.	112	204	52	32	2.99	.855	Accepted
5	I am motivated to perform well in school because my parents provide both care and structure.	120	160	80	40	2.90	.945	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.032$ SD= .8964								Accepted

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.81, 3.28, 3.18, 2.99, and 2.90 with corresponding standard deviations of .968, .896, .818, .855, and .945 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.032 with the cluster standard deviation of .8964 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that authoritative parenting style has influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *How does authoritarian parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students?*

Table 2: Analysis of Influence of Authoritarian Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	My parents expect me to follow school rules without questioning.	320	60	20	0	3.75	.537	Accepted
7	My parents focus more on discipline than on my personal academic struggles.	160	180	40	20	3.20	.813	Accepted
8	I often feel pressured to meet my parents' strict academic demands.	128	120	80	72	2.76	1.089	Accepted
9	My parents rarely explain the reasons behind their academic expectations.	120	240	32	8	3.18	.655	Accepted
10	I sometimes feel anxious about academics because of my parents' rigid rules.	140	164	56	40	3.01	.945	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.18$ SD= .8078								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.75, 3.20, 2.76, 3.18, and 3.01 with corresponding standard deviations of .537, .813, 1.089, .655, and .945 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.18 with the cluster standard deviation of .8078 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that authoritarian parenting

style has influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: *How does permissive parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students?*

Table 3: Analysis of Influence of Permissive Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	My parents allow me to make most decisions about my studies.	172	168	0	60	3.13	1.008	Accepted
12	I have little supervision from my parents concerning my schoolwork.	88	246	6	60	2.91	.910	Accepted
13	My parents rarely enforce rules regarding my academic responsibilities.	176	146	18	60	3.10	1.039	Accepted
14	I sometimes neglect schoolwork because my parents do not insist on discipline.	82	234	24	60	2.85	.918	Accepted
15	I feel less motivated to study because my parents are very lenient about school matters.	186	136	0	78	3.08	1.115	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.014$ SD= .998								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 are 3.13, 2.91, 3.10, 2.85, and 3.08 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.008, .910, 1.039, .918, and 1.115 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.438 with the cluster standard deviation of .5804 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that permissive parenting style has influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Research Question 4: *How does neglectful parenting style influence the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students?*

Table 4: Analysis of Influence of Neglectful Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
16	My parents hardly monitor my academic progress.	120	160	80	40	2.90	.945	Accepted
17	I do not get guidance or support from my parents in my schoolwork.	320	60	20	0	3.75	.537	Accepted
18	I often struggle with academics because my parents are uninvolved.	160	180	40	20	3.20	.813	Accepted
19	My parents rarely attend to my educational needs or challenges.	183	139	42	36	3.17	.946	Accepted
20	I feel neglected in my academics because my parents show little concern for my studies.	170	172	1	57	3.14	.990	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.232$ SD= .8462								Accepted

Table 4 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 16 to 20 are 2.90, 3.75, 3.20, 3.17, and 3.14 with corresponding standard deviations of .945, .537, .813, .946, and .990 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.232 with the cluster standard deviation of .8462 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that neglectful parenting

style has influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Authoritative parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of Influence of Authoritative Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	96.320	.000	Sig.
SA	100	100.0					
A	180	100.0					
D	64	100.0					
SD	56	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 96.320$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that authoritative parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria is therefore, rejected. This implies that authoritative parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

Authoritarian parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of Influence of Authoritarian Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	200.00	.000	Sig.
SA	160	100.0					
A	180	100.0					
D	40	100.0					
SD	20	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 200.00$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that authoritarian parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria is therefore, rejected. This implies that authoritarian parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3

Permissive parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students.

Table 7: Chi-square Test of Influence of Permissive Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	256.560	.000	Sig.
SA	82	100.0					
A	234	100.0					
D	24	100.0					
SD	60	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 7 revealed that $\chi^2 = 256.560$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that permissive parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria is therefore, rejected. This implies that permissive parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 4

Neglectful parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students.

Table 8: Chi-square Test of Influence of Neglectful Parenting Style on the Academic Adjustment of Senior Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	158.700	.000	Sig.
SA	183	100.0					
A	139	100.0					
D	42	100.0					
SD	36	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 8 revealed that $\chi^2 = 158.700$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that neglectful parenting style has no significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria is therefore, rejected. This implies that neglectful parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research is organized around the research questions and hypotheses for ease of reading and comprehension. The four null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding revealed that authoritative parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. This finding suggests that students who are raised in homes where parents combine warmth with clear rules and expectations tend to adjust better academically. Such students are more likely to develop positive study habits, stay motivated, and manage school-related challenges with confidence. This is because authoritative parents encourage independence while still providing guidance, which enhances the child’s self-regulation and commitment to academic responsibilities. Supporting this view, Alami et al. (2019) found that students raised under authoritative parenting displayed higher levels of academic self-efficacy and engagement compared to peers from less supportive homes. Similarly, Dada and Adebayo (2021) reported that authoritative parenting fosters responsibility, emotional stability, and discipline, all of which promote better adjustment to academic demands.

The second finding revealed that authoritarian parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. This result indicates that strict and controlling parental practices also shape the way students adapt to school demands. Although authoritarian parents emphasize obedience and discipline, the outcome can be double-edged: some students may comply and perform well due to fear of punishment, while others may struggle with anxiety, low self-esteem, and reduced intrinsic motivation. The influence is therefore significant but not always positive. Research supports this interpretation. For instance, Wang et al. (2018) observed that authoritarian parenting can increase academic pressure, sometimes leading to surface-level learning rather than deep engagement. In the Nigerian context, Adeyemi and Oyediran (2020) also noted that authoritarian homes produce students who may adjust academically through compliance but often lack creativity and problem-solving skills needed for long-term success.

The third finding revealed that permissive parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. The finding implies that lenient parenting, where rules and expectations are minimal, also affects students' academic adjustment. Students from such homes may initially enjoy freedom and less pressure, but in the long run, they often face challenges with discipline, time management, and academic consistency. This weakens their ability to adapt to structured academic settings where responsibility and self-control are crucial. Corroborating this, Aluko (2019) found that permissive parenting was associated with poor study habits and lower academic persistence among secondary school students in Lagos. Likewise, Nwosu and Chukwuma (2021) revealed that children raised under permissive parenting tend to show higher levels of distraction and poorer adjustment when confronted with demanding academic environments.

The fourth finding revealed that neglectful parenting style has significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. This outcome points to the fact that when parents show little involvement in their children's lives, students' academic adjustment suffers greatly. Neglectful parenting deprives students of both emotional support and guidance, leaving them vulnerable to academic stress, low motivation, and in many cases, poor performance. Students in such conditions often struggle with self-regulation and may disengage from school altogether. In line with this, Hassan and Yusuf (2017) found that neglectful parenting strongly predicted academic maladjustment, absenteeism, and declining performance among secondary school students. More recently, Odo and Ede (2022) emphasized that students from neglectful homes often lack the emotional stability and resilience needed to cope with academic challenges, which worsens their overall adjustment.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study established that authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful parenting styles each have significant influence on the academic adjustment of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt City, Nigeria. The findings highlight the vital role of parental practices in shaping how adolescents adapt to academic demands, manage stress, and achieve scholastic success. It underscores the need for parents, educators, and counsellors to recognize the implications of parenting styles on students' overall academic adjustment. Based on these findings the following recommendations are made:

1. Parents should be encouraged to adopt the authoritative style since it fosters balance between discipline and support, thereby enhancing students' confidence, motivation, and adjustment to academic demands.
2. Parents who tend toward authoritarian methods should be sensitized through parenting seminars and school-based programs to apply discipline with warmth and effective communication, so that strictness does not hinder students' positive adjustment.
3. Parents practicing permissiveness should be guided to set reasonable boundaries for their children. This will help students develop self-control, responsibility, and better academic focus without feeling neglected or overly indulged.

4. Awareness campaigns should be carried out to discourage neglectful parenting. Parents should be educated on the dangers of emotional and academic neglect and be encouraged to invest time, attention, and support in their children's schooling.

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